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TREATMENT OF DYUSHEN MUSCULAR DYSTROPHY WITH APPLICATION OF FETAL PROGENER CELL TRANSPLANTATION

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ЛЕЧЕНИЕ МЫШЕЧНОЙ ДИСТРОФИИ ДЮШЕННА С ПРИМЕНЕНИЕМ ТРАНСПЛАНТАЦИИ ФЕТАЛЬНЫХ ПРОГЕНИТОРНЫХ КЛЕТОК

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Summary/Резюме

The authors are reviewing issues arising in the process of treatment of Duchenne muscular dystrophy (DMD) – a recessive X-linked disorder. This study focused on the effectiveness of the developed DMD treatment method.

Results. The study included 35 patients with DMD aged from 5 to 19 who underwent fetal stem cell transplantation.

Laboratory tests before the treatment were remarkable for significant elevation of CPK in all the patients. Many patients also had high levels of ALT, ACT and LDH.

Administration of stem cells directly into the affected muscles (intramuscularly) results in higher muscle tone, muscle bulk growth stimulation, muscle power and physical capacity increase, immune boosting, improved cognitive and intellectual skills and psycho-emotional state in general.

Key words: *Duchenne muscular dystrophy, stem cells, fetal progenitor cells, myoblasts, multi-point intramuscular administration.*

Авторы рассматривают проблемы, возникающие в процессе лечения мышечной дистрофии Дюшенна (МДД) - рецессивного X-сцепленного расстройства. Данное исследование было сосредоточено на эффективности разработанного метода лечения МДД.

Полученные результаты. В исследование были включены 35 пациентов с МДД в возрасте от 5 до 19 лет, которым была проведена трансплантация эмбриональных стволовых клеток.

Лабораторные тесты до лечения были отмечены значительным повышением КФК у всех пациентов. Многие пациенты также имели высокий уровень ALT, АСТ и LDH.

Введение стволовых клеток непосредственно в пораженные мышцы (внутримышечно) приводит к повышению мышечного тонуса, стимуляции роста мышечной массы, увеличению мышечной силы и физических возможностей, повышению иммунитета, улучшению когнитивных и интеллектуальных навыков и психоэмоционального состояния в целом.

Ключевые слова: мышечная дистрофия Дюшенна, стволовые клетки, клетки-предшественники плода, миобласты, многоточечное внутримышечное введение.

Автори розглядають проблеми, що виникають в процесі лікування м'язової дистрофії Дюшенна (МДД) - рецесивного Х-зчепленого розладу. Дане дослідження було зосереджено на ефективності розробленого методу лікування МДД.

Отримані результати. У дослідження були включені 35 пацієнта з МДД у віці від 5 до 19 років, яким була проведена трансплантація ембріональних стовбурових клітин.

Лабораторні тести до лікування були відзначені значним підвищенням КФК у всіх пацієнтів. Багато пацієнтів також мали високий рівень ALT, АСТ і LDH.

Введення стовбурових клітин безпосередньо в уражені м'язи (внутрішньом'язово) призводить до підвищення м'язового тонусу, стимуляції росту м'язової маси, збільшення м'язової сили і фізичних можливостей, підвищенню імунітету, поліпшенню когнітивних і інтелектуальних навичок і психоемоційного стану в цілому.

Ключові слова: м'язова дистрофія Дюшенна, стовбурові клітини, клітини-попередники плода, міобласти, багатоточкове внутрішньом'язове введення.

Rationale

Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy (DMD) is a hereditary X-linked recessive disorder caused by abnormal dystrophin synthesis due to genetic defect and resulting in progressive muscular degeneration [1].

According to different sources, DMD affects around 1 in 4, 000 – 6,000 people internationally [2]. On the average, the disease is diagnosed at the age of 3-5 when physical capacity of the affected child is markedly different from that of healthy peers[3]. It is believed that during the first years of DMD patient life his/her muscle fibers regenerate by means of own stem cells of the muscle differon the reserve of

which gradually depletes, which leads to abnormal dystrophin production causing muscle degeneration and fibrosis [4].

Rapidly progressive muscle weakness results in gait problems in teenage years. Wheelchair is usually needed by the age of 9-11, but each case is individual. Apart from the progressive muscle weakness, more that 50% of the patients have dystrophin deficiency-induced cardiovascular issues by the age of 15 [5]. In patients aged 20 and older, diaphragm and muscles regulating lung function weaken significantly, therefore they can die from respiratory failure [6]. Gastrointestinal and excretory systems, as well as intellect, are also affected [7].

Over the last years, stem cells are used for DMD treatment [8]. In our opinion, stem cells isolated from fetal muscles can differentiate into myocytes, which suggests that stem cell therapy can be effective in DMD.

The authors are of the opinion that the proposed approaches to treatment will result in higher quality of life and longer life span of DMD patients.

The goal of work is to study clinical effectiveness of the elaborated method of fetal progenitor cell transplantation in DMD.

Materials and Methods

The study included 35 male patients with DMD aged from 5 to 19 examined before and after fetal stem cell (FSCT).

Stem cells were isolated in the Em-ProCell (Mumbai, India) biotechnological laboratory in accordance with international GMP standards.

Stem cells were isolated at the time of organogenesis (beginning stages of muscle system formation) and thoroughly tested for biological safety, aerobic and anaerobic microorganisms, and fungi. Screening also included real time PCR for 12 types of bacteria, genetic testing and karyotyping (XY) [9].

In the course of research, treatment method based on application of fetal progenitor cells and fetal tissue extracts aimed at dystrophin production deficit compensation has been developed. The underlying principle of treatment is transfer of normal (healthy) genetic information of the fetal myoblasts cell nucleus into patient's muscle. Implantation of nuclei of fetal progenitor cells with normal genes encoding synthesis of all 79 exons of dystrophin [10] results in restoration of dystrophin production. Inhibition of muscle tissue degeneration gives time for repeated transplantations of fetal stem cells, which, at the end, results in longer life expectancy and higher life quality in most DMD patients.

Stem cells were administered according to our developed method that included transplantation of two types of allogenic fetal progenitor cells from the same fetus: hematopoietic cells of fetal liver for immune tolerance induction thank to which fetal myoblasts (allogenic muscular cells) administered by multiple intramuscular injections at the next stage are treated by the body like its own [11].

For optimal clinical result, we performed additional subcutaneous administration of fetal myoblasts and fetal placenta extracts containing cytokines stimulating growth and differentiation of both patient's own and transplanted fetal stem cell.

Our method resulted in positive results in Duchenne and myotonic muscular dystrophies as well as in myositis and motor neuron disease.

As a part of the study that lasted for 5 years, many DMD patients repeated stem cells therapy aimed at dystrophin production deficit compensation.

Results and Discussion.

For optimal clinical effect in DMD, combination of stem cells and fetal tissues extracts is selected individually for each case of DMD and its complications. This treatment results in the following:

- inhibition of the disease progression (longer period of independent ambulation etc.)
- preservation of muscle and physical power
- gait quality improvement (in walking patients)
- improvement or restoration of some skills (climbing stairs, combing, getting up from the floor or sitting position)
- reduction of pseudohypertrophy or muscle straining
- decreased values of ALT, CPK and LDH signifying subsidence of inflammation in the muscle tissue

Table 1 Laboratory tests performed before the treatment demonstrated marked CPK elevation in all the patients. Many patients also had elevated ALT and LDH. Functional condition was evaluated on Muscular Dystrophy Functional Rating Scale (MDFRS) (Table 1) [12, 14].

Muscular Dystrophy Functional Rating Scale			
Domains			
Mobility	Basic activities of daily life	Arm function	Functional Impairment
1 Stair climbing	1 Feeding	1 Managing objects over head	1 Severity of upper limb joint contracture
2 Outdoor mobility	2 Combing hair	2 Carrying objects	2 Severity of lower limb joint contractures
3 Indoor mobility	3 Brushing teeth	3 Cleaning table	3 Number of contracted joints in the upper limbs
4 Transfers from bed to chair	4 Dressing upper/lower parts of body	4 Writing	4 Number of contracted joints in the lower limbs
5 Wheelchair manipulation	5 Toileting	5 Turning pages of a book	5 Severity of neck contracture
6 Standing from sitting	6 Bathing	6 Picking up small objects	6 Strength of the neck
7 Sitting from lying		7 Managing objects over head	7 Strength of the trunk
8 Rolling			8 Scoliosis
9 Changing body position in bed			9 Orthopnea
			10 Sputum clearance
			11 Ventilator assisted
Total for Mobility =	Total for Basic activities of daily life =	Total for Arm function =	Total for Impairment =
Total Score =			

We performed mathematical analysis of DMD treatment effectiveness.

The preliminary analysis demonstrated significant differences in both baseline functional/biochemical parameters and their changes 3

- prevention or subsidence of the symptoms of myopathy complications
- improved function of internal organs and systems
- intellect and psycho-emotional state improvement, higher self-esteem
- immune boosting
- life quality improvement

The results of treatment with fetal myoblasts are different in each patient.

and 6 months after FSCT in the study participants.

First treatment effectiveness evaluation was based on general functional status changes. In 4 patients, MDFRS score increased from $48,7 \pm 1,8$ to $58,8 \pm 1,8$ within 3 months and then to $64,0 \pm 2,9$ within 6 months (Fig.1). Net differences were $+10,0 \pm 1,6$ i $+15,3 \pm 1,9$ accordingly, which gives us reason to regard such pattern as rapidly progressive. Progressive general

Fig.1 Four patterns of individual changes in general functional status by MDFRS: rapidly progressive (rp), slowly progressive (sp), stagnant (s) and reverse (r). In each, triad, the first column is baseline, second – results 3 months after FSCT and third – results 6 months after FSCT. All patients are coded.

Fig. 2. Correlation between CPhK, LDH and ALT changes (X) and MDPRS (Y) 3 months after FSCT.

Fig. 3. Correlation between CPhK, LDH and ALT changes (X) and MDPRS (Y) 6 months after FSCT.

MDPRS score increased from $43,6 \pm 0,6$ to $47,1 \pm 0,6$ and to $51,4 \pm 1,0$ accordingly, while net differences were $+3,5 \pm 0,4$ and $+7,8 \pm 0,7$ accordingly. Unfortunately, in 10 patients MDPRS score that increased to $4,6 \pm 1,6$ (from $39,5 \pm 0,8$ to $44,1 \pm 1,8$) within first three months remain practically unchanged in the course of the following three months - $43,3 \pm 1,8$, which was regarded as stagnation. In another 5 children, the first elevation from $39,8 \pm 1,3$ to $47,4 \pm 2,1$ was followed by the decreased to $44,6 \pm 2,1$, and this pattern was regarded as reverse.

Correlation analysis demonstrates that general functional status improvement goes parallel with reduced activity of plasma enzymes, or their reduced release from myocytes into the blood. It is interesting to note that 3 months after the

functional status improvement, though slow, was also reported in 16 children:

treatment, MDPRS score changes are equally determined

Table 2

Discriminant Function Analysis Summary
Step 6, N of vars in model: 6; Grouping: 4 grps
Wilks' Lambda: 0,066; approx. $F_{(19)}=6,63$; $p < 10^{-6}$

Variables currently in the model	Wilks' Λ	Partial Λ	F-remove	p-level	Tolerance
Creatinphosphokinase-6DB, IU/L	0,109	0,604	5,7	0,004	0,495
MDPRS-6DB, points	0,158	0,418	12,1	10,anp	0,168
MDPRS-3DB, points	0,121	0,547	7,2	0,001	0,164
Alaninaminotransferase-6DB, IU/L	0,086	0,772	2,6	0,077	0,63
Lactatdehydrogenase-6DB, IU/L	0,081	0,815	2	0,144	0,198
Lactatdehydrogenase-3DB, IU/L	0,076	0,867	1,3	0,285	0,229
Variables currently not in the model	Wilks' Λ	Partial Λ	F to enter	p-level	Tolerance
Alaninaminotransferase-3DB, IU/L	0,061	0,926	0,67	0,579	0,293
Creatinphosphokinase-3DB, IU/L	0,062	0,931	0,62	0,61	0,328

Table 3

Summary of Stepwise Analysis

Variables currently in the model	F to enter	p-level	Λ	F-value	p-level
Creatinphosphokinase-6DB, IU/L	8,5	10^{-3}	,550	8,5	10^{-3}
MDPRS-6DB, points	7,9	10^{-3}	,306	8,1	10^{-5}
MDPRS-3DB, points	11,6	10^{-4}	,139	9,8	10^{-5}
Alaninaminotransferase-6DB, IU/L	4,0	,018	,098	8,7	10^{-6}
Lactatdehydrogenase-6DB, IU/L	2,5	,078	,076	7,7	10^{-6}
Lactatdehydrogenase-3DB, IU/L	1,3	,285	,066	6,6	10^{-6}

by ALT and CPhK changes without significant LDH change (Fig.2), while 6 months after FSCT CPhK importance significantly increases, while determination importance of LDH increases to that of ALT, which remains unchanged (Fig.3).

For visualization and creation of the coherent enzyme picture of each pattern, forward stepwise discriminant function analysis of

Fig. 4. Individual values of roots 1 and 2 with condensed information about MDFRS changes and elevated enzymes in children with different patterns of post-treatment changes.

Fig. 5. Individual values of roots 1 and 3 with condensed information about MDFRS changes and elevated enzymes in children with different patterns of post-treatment changes.

(Wilks' $\Lambda = 0,427$; $\chi^2_{(10)} = 25$; $p = 0,006$), for the third - $0,479$ (Wilks' $\Lambda = 0,771$; $\chi^2_{(4)} = 8$; $p = 0,110$). The other measure of the discriminative power of the root is its percentage amounting to 83,2%, 12,3% and 4,5% accordingly.

Table 4 presents raw (actual) and standardized (scaled) discriminant variables coefficients. Raw coefficient provides information about the **absolute** contribution of the given variable to the discriminant function value, while standardized coefficients reflect **relative** contribution of the variable, irrespective of the unit of measure. They allow for detection of variables with max contribution to the value of the discriminant function.

Table 5 presents full structural coefficients – coefficient of correlation between discriminant root and variables. Structural coefficient demonstrates closeness of connection between variables and discriminant functions, or what part of information about discriminant function (root) is stored in the given variable.

The sum of the products of raw coefficients (Table 4) by discriminant variables value (Table 5) with constant (Table 4) give the value of discriminant function (root) for each child and allow for its visualization in the information field of the roots (Figs. 2 and 3).

As we can see (Fig. 4), the extreme left position along the first root axis are children with least favorable functional changes along with minimal CPhK activity changes 6 months after the treatment and minimal LDH changes 3 and 6 months after the treatment. At the same time, delineation of reverse and stagnation pattern

the available data was performed [Klecka WR, 1989] [13]. The program chose 6 parameters (their changes) (D) to be included into the model, while the remaining 2 were not in the model (Tables 2 and 3).

After this, 6-D space of discriminant variables is transformed into 3-D space of canonical roots, which are linear combination of discriminant variables.

Discriminative power of the root characterizes canonical correlation coefficient (r^*) as a measure of connection and degree of dependency between the groups and discriminant function. For the first root, it equals to $0,919$ (Wilks' $\Lambda = 0,066$; $\chi^2_{(18)} = 79$; $p < 10^{-6}$), for the second - $0,667$

Standardized and Raw Coefficients and Constants for Canonical Variables

Coefficients Variables currently in the model	Standardized			Raw		
	Root 1	Root 2	Root 3	Root 1	Root 2	Root 3
Creatinphosphokinase-6DB, IU/L	0,856	-0,48	0,59	3E-04	-0	2E-04
MDFRS-6DB, points	1,963	-0,21	-0,9	0,442	-0,05	-0,2
MDFRS-3DB, points	-1,77	-0,43	0,268	-0,41	-0,1	0,063
Alaninaminotransferase-6DB, IU/L	0,066	0,881	-0,23	0,004	0,048	-0,01
Lactatdehydrogenase-6DB, IU/L	-0,8	0,276	-1,25	-0,01	0,002	-0,01
Lactatdehydrogenase-3DB, IU/L	0,279	-0,81	0,996	0,003	-0,01	0,01
Constants				0,427	1,316	1,466
Eigenvalues				5,466	0,804	0,297
Cumulative Properties, %				0,832	0,832	0,955

Table 4 representatives is somewhat ill-defined. The extreme right position belongs to the children with progressive improvements, without clear delineation between slow and fast progression. It should be noted that stagnant pattern is delineated along the second root axis by holding the top positions, which shows minimal reduction of ALT activity 6 months after the treatment.

Correlations Variables-Canonical Roots, Centroides of Roots and Means of Changes in Variables

Variables currently in the model	Root 1	Root 2	Root 3	Rec	Stag	SlowPro	RapPro
Root 1 (83,2%)				-3,31	-2,1	1,86	1,95
Creatinphosphokinase-6DB, In IU/L	0,38	0,013	0,313	-0,85	-0,94	-1,19	-1,57
Lactatdehydrogenase-3DB, In IU/L	-0,07	-0,22	0,397	-0,14	-0,29	-0,29	-0,4
Lactatdehydrogenase-6DB, In IU/L	-0,1	-0,08	0,069	-0,21	-0,29	-0,39	-0,45
Root 2 (12,3%)				-1,49	0,97	0,12	-1,02
Alaninaminotransferase-6DB, In IU/L	0,211	0,647	0,003	-0,7	-0,51	-0,63	-0,85
Root 3 (4,5%)				0,4	-0,27	0,35	-1,2
MDFRS-3DB, points	-0,06	-0,44	-0,66	7,6	4,6	3,5	10
MDFRS-6DB, points	0,253	-0,42	-0,77	4,8	3,8	7,8	15,3

Table 5 At the same time, patients with slow and fast progression are delineated along third root axis demonstrating MD-FRS changes (Fig.5).

Squared Mahalanobis Distances, F-values and p-levels

Pattern of changes	Stagnant	Rapidly Progressive	Slowly Progressive	Reverse
Stagnant	0,0	24,0	18,9	9,0
Rapidly Progressive	7,5 <10 ⁻⁴	0,0	4,2	34,4
Slowly Progressive	14,9 <10 ⁻⁶	1,5 0,230	0,0	33,1
Reverse	3,5 0,012	8,3 <10 ⁻⁴	14,6 <10 ⁻⁶	0,0

Table 6 Generally speaking, delineation of all four patterns in the information space of the three canonical roots is quite clear, which is documented by calculation of Mahalanobis distances between cluster centroids (Table 6).

Coefficients and Constants for Classification Functions

Pattern of Changes	Stagnant	Rapidly Progressive	Slowly Progressive	Reverse
Variables	p= 0,286	p=0,1149	p=0,457	p=0,143
Creatinphosphokinase-6DB, IU/L	-0	1E-04	2E-04	-0
MDFRS-6DB, points	-0,47	1,605	1,197	-1,02
MDFRS-3DB, points	0,303	-1,23	-1,21	1,099
Alaninaminotransferase-6DB, IU/L	-0,1	-0,17	-0,13	-0,23
Lactatdehydrogenase-6DB, IU/L	0,035	0,014	0,002	0,031
Lactatdehydrogenase-3DB, IU/L	-0,04	-0,02	-0,02	-0,02
Constants	-10,3	-13,9	-7,47	-17,8

Table 7 These discriminant parameters can be used for identification (classification) of the patient's belonging to a certain pattern. This goal of the discriminant analysis is fulfilled through the use of classifying (dis-

criminant) functions (Table 7).

These functions are special linear combinations maximizing differences between the groups and minimizing dispersion inside them. Classification function coefficients are raw, therefore they are not interpreted. The object belongs to the group with the maximum value of the function calculated by adding up products of variables value x classification function coefficients + constant.

Table 8 demonstrates practically integral precision of retrospective identification. The data received confirm individual nature of recovery in DMD, but, at the same time, they evidence that they can be divided into four general clusters with two patterns of reaction to SC administration in each – slowly and rapidly progressive.

The parameters obtained also allow for distribution of children into different classes (classification) and prognosis of further course of the disease after stem cell therapy. Thus, the use of the proposed mathematical analysis allows for prognosis and control of individual effectiveness of DMD treatment with stem cells.

Thus, the analysis suggests that stem cell treatment peculiarities and effectiveness depends on individual reaction nature, while MDFRS changes pattern depends on the child's age and other parameters to be studied in the forthcoming research.

The next article will shed light on the possibility of prognosis of the detected patterns of functional and biochemical changes.

Conclusions

1. The proposed method of fetal progenitor cell administration is an

Table 8

Classification Matrix
Rows: Observed classifications
Columns: Predicted classifications

Pattern of Changes	Percent Correct	Stagnant	Rapidly Progressive	Slowly Progressive	Recurrent
Stagnant	100	10	0	0	0
Rapidly Progressive	75,0	0	3	1	0
Slowly Progressive	100	0	0	16	0
Reverse	100	0	0	0	5
Total	97,1	10	3	17	5

effective and promising therapeutic approach in DMD.

2. Administration of stem cells directly into the affected muscles is clinically effective and results in positive biochemical changes.
3. Stem cell therapy effectiveness is, to a great extent, determined by the individual nature of reaction.

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